

Effect of Access to Financial Services on the Growth of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of access to financial services on the growth and expansion of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria. The study utilised a mixed-methods research design which integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive analysis. The targeted population includes SMEs operating in various sectors such as manufacturing, services, trade, and agriculture. The study used a structured questionnaire as research instrument and data was analysed using descriptive statistics for demographic profiling and inferential statistics specifically correlation analysis and linear regression. The findings revealed that while a significant number of SMEs are formally banked, true financial inclusion remains limited due to accessibility issues, high borrowing costs, and limited product offerings. The study concluded that while financial services play a crucial role in SME growth, other factors such as financial literacy, economic conditions, and policy frameworks must be considered to address the growth challenges faced by SMEs. The study therefore recommended that financial institutions and government agencies should collaborate to provide financial literacy programs, workshops, and seminars for SME owners and managers. This will enhance their ability to make informed financial decisions and effectively utilise financial services.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), Financial services, Business growth, Exchange rate

Word Counts: 192

Introduction

Businesses' economic success, especially small and medium-sized organisations, is greatly influenced by exchange rates. This is because SMEs have limited resources and are exposed to global markets. The Bretton Woods system, established in the aftermath of World War II, brought stability to global trade. The system gradually collapsed during the 1970s stemming from escalating economic differences and speculative currency attacks. With the adoption of floating exchange rate regimes, many currencies experienced devaluation, enhancing the global appeal of exports while increasing the volume of imports. This shift has influenced the operational costs faced by small and medium-sized enterprises. Nigeria's oil-dependent economy has been greatly impacted by currency devaluation, which has undermined the

international competitiveness of its small and medium-sized enterprises in the export market (Okwara & Okechukwu, 2024). The exchange rate strategy maintained in Nigeria since 1986 has caused the naira to be overvalued, leading to a rise in imports and a decline in non-oil exports. As a result, there was an excessive reliance on foreign resources. The naira's value versus the dollar was greatly affected by the global economic crisis, causing the exchange rate to rise from N120/1\$ to over N180/1\$ between 2008 and 2009. The exchange rate is vital in determining a nation's balance of payments position and ensuring price stability. Nevertheless, Nigeria's global trade structure, which is mostly focused on crude oil and agricultural products, does not fulfil the criteria for a successful balance of payments plan (Irmiya, Agbo, & Odumu, 2023).

Fluctuations in exchange rates have an impact on prices, leading to a redistribution of money among suppliers, customers, and competitors. They can have a detrimental effect on the competitiveness of a sector. Currency depreciation can enhance the profitability of exporting firms by reducing prices in foreign markets. However, it can also diminish revenues if companies acquire intermediate goods, resulting in increased production costs. Even organisations that are not operating on an international scale may nevertheless be impacted by these swings through indirect means (Belghitar et al., 2021). The depreciation of the Naira has generated public interest in currency exchange rate volatility, impacting performance of enterprises in Nigeria. The fluctuation of currency exchange rates is of utmost importance for multinational corporations' financial operations, as foreign currencies play a vital role in international trade. Exchange rates are a fluctuating macroeconomic variable that has an impact on business activities (Olaoye & Olaniyi, 2023).

Financial inclusion, a global strategy aimed at addressing poverty and inadequate access to financial services seeks to offer affordable availability of diverse financial options such as payment solutions, savings accounts, loans, insurance, and retirement plans. It is essential in supporting the development and progress of small and medium businesses. The Central Bank of Nigeria is actively pursuing financial inclusion through microfinance, addressing challenges faced by SMEs in Nigeria, such as hostile business environments, inadequate capital, limited managerial expertise, and lack of access to modern technology (Ogidi & Pam, 2021). However, the banks face challenges in obtaining funds, including inadequate business plans, marketing strategies, efficient accounting systems, and managerial issues. These obstacles hinder MSMEs' participation in banking services, particularly loans, crucial for their expansion. The National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS) has not yielded significant results due to these challenges (Ilemona & Olaniyi, 2023). Furthermore, small and medium enterprises continue to struggle with obtaining or assimilating new technology, develop their operations to engage in international markets, or establish business connections (Ayunku & Pakepinene, 2023).

It was stated that access to financial services has the ability to improve the effectiveness of linking savings to investments, as well as facilitate adjustments in the financial system's framework. The advantages of financial inclusion in Nigeria have been praised, but concerns persist, particularly among small and medium-scale businesses. The issues encompass the absence of financial services, cyber theft, deceitful practices, undisclosed expenses, refusal to accept Nigerian cards for global transactions, faulty ATMs, and interruptions in network connectivity. The challenge of acquiring access to funding remains a significant barrier to establishing new enterprises (Ayunku & Pakepinene, 2023). Policy makers, academics and development agencies are increasingly acknowledging the global significance of access to financial services as a tool for driving economic growth. This is especially true in terms of eliminating extreme poverty, generating employment opportunities, and fostering wealth

creation and sustainable livelihoods (Yunus et al., 2023). The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of access to financial services on the growth and expansion of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria.

Literature Review

Financial Inclusion among SMEs

Financial inclusion refers to a condition where both individuals and businesses can obtain financial products and services should be affordable, relevant, and provided in a responsible and sustainable manner. These offerings encompass payments, transactions, investments, credit, borrowing, savings, and insurance. Financial inclusion strategies refer to the plans or action frameworks developed at national or regional levels to promote or expand financial inclusion. To be effective, these strategies must coordinate key stakeholders' efforts, clearly define roles, and establish resource planning with measurable goals. Such strategies often encourage streamlined and effective processes to achieve meaningful advancements in financial inclusion, usually developed in partnership with the private sector to establish and pursue shared, realistic objectives. A holistic approach to enhancing financial inclusion typically emphasises three main elements: the availability of financial products and services, the actual utilisation of these offerings, and the quality of the financial services provided (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008).

Financing Sources

Venture Capital

Venture capital serves as an alternative funding source for SMEs worldwide, in both advanced and emerging economies, this type of financing provides investment funds to SMEs using equity or quasi-equity instruments that are not traded on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Venture capital is often considered risk capital, focusing mainly on fast-growing companies in their early stages. Typically, venture capital is divided into two categories: seed capital and start-up or early-stage capital. In reality, venture capitalists also supply funding for business expansion, growth projects, and buyouts targeting SMEs (Wang, 2019). Venture capitalists act as financial intermediaries, offering an alternative non-bank source of funding to SMEs. These investors supply both capital and strategic support to businesses seeking growth but lacking access to traditional equity markets. Venture capital involves reallocating investor funds into high-risk ventures, typically start-ups or early-stage companies. This form of financing is particularly common among small and emerging SMEs within well-developed financial markets (Wang, 2019).

Trade Credits

Trade credit plays a vital role as a funding mechanism for SMEs. It occurs when SMEs acquire goods or services from suppliers with payment postponed to a later date. Typically, trade credit is short-term, with payment expected within 30 to 90 days. Failure to settle within this timeframe usually results in interest penalties. Apart from traditional bank loans, trade credit is widely used globally to finance SMEs and is recognised as a significant external funding source in both developed and developing economies. This form of financing arises naturally from everyday business transactions, making it a spontaneous funding option for SMEs. The cost of

trade credit is generally incorporated into the price of goods sold on credit, which often makes it a relatively costly means of financing. Moreover, the duration of trade credit is often limited, particularly when suppliers are large firms that perceive SMEs as higher risk, restricting the extension of payment terms. When SMEs present greater risk, suppliers tend to be hesitant to prolong credit periods further. Despite some drawbacks, trade credit remains an essential funding avenue, especially for newly established SMEs (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023).

Crowd Funding

Crowdfunding is a method of raising capital online by collecting small contributions from a large number of people, often referred to as "the crowd," to support a business venture. Though relatively recent, this approach has rapidly expanded, generating billions of dollars globally through more than 500 crowdfunding platforms and launching over 400 campaigns each day. Funds raised via crowdfunding can be allocated either as debt or equity investments in the business seeking support. A key aspect of crowdfunding is the interactive nature of the online community, similar to a physical crowd, where enthusiastic backers frequently encourage others to participate. This dynamic enables individuals to discover and invest in projects or ideas that interest them, often making them willing to accept higher risks and lower returns than usual. Crowdfunding offers SMEs a valuable opportunity to engage directly with investors who are open to financing innovative and technology-driven ventures typical of small businesses. However, there are risks: if the funding target is not reached, no funds may be received. Additionally, reward-based campaigns often attract many supporters but yield small contributions since investors receive no ownership stake. Some crowdfunding platforms also charge substantial fees, which can reduce the overall funds available to the business (Olayinka, 2022). Since 2015, there has been a noticeable rise in efforts by the Nigerian government and regulatory bodies to actively implement policies designed to enhance financial inclusion. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has played a leading role in fostering and backing financial products aimed particularly at low-income and underserved populations.

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

There is no single, universally agreed-upon definition, whether operational or quantitative for what constitutes a small-scale enterprise (World Bank, 2022). In Nigeria, a commonly agreed-upon definition for small-sized enterprises does not exist (Beck et al., 2020). The definition of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often varies depending on the context and the objectives of the defining body. According to the World Bank, SMEs are characterised by having up to 300 employees, annual sales not exceeding \$15 million, and assets capped at \$15 million. In the United Kingdom, small-scale industries are classified as those with annual revenues of £2 million or less and employing fewer than 200 paid workers, without any mention of capital investment. Kenya defines small businesses as those employing fewer than five individuals, while medium-sized enterprises employ between 50 and 200 workers. In Vietnam, SMEs are identified as firms with a workforce ranging from 10 to 300 employees, whereas in Egypt, the classification covers businesses employing more than five but fewer than 50 people. Definitions also differ by country: Japan and the United States generally consider companies with 300 to 500 employees as SMEs, while Indonesia defines small businesses as those with fewer than 10 full-time staff. To capture industry-specific differences and guide SME-targeted policies, the U.S. Small Business Administration's Size Standard Office determines SME classifications, defining small businesses as those with fewer than 500 employees (Small Business Administration, 2021). The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) describes SMEs as small-scale enterprises operating with annual turnovers up to ₦500,000,

aligned with the limit set by the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS), and up to ₦1,000,000. Meanwhile, in 2015, the National Council of Industry defined a small-scale business as one employing between 11 and 100 people, with total capital investment covering working capital but excluding land costs below ₦50 million.

Theoretical Review

This study employed Financial Inclusion Theory. The concept of financial inclusion has been developed and advocated by several researchers and international organisations over the years. Thorsten Beck, a well-known advocate of this idea, has conducted considerable research that emphasises the significance of financial development and inclusion in promoting economic growth and alleviating poverty. Beck, together with other researchers such as Asli Demirgüç-Kunt and Patrick Honohan, has established the foundation for comprehending the ways in which having access to financial services may enhance the capabilities of people and organisations, resulting in wider economic advantages (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008).

The notion of financial inclusion is based on three fundamental assumptions. Firstly, it presupposes that having access to a diverse array of financial services, such as savings, credit, insurance, and payment services, empowers people and enterprises to enhance their financial welfare (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008). This access facilitates the process of consuming goods and services, mitigating risks, and capitalising on development prospects. Furthermore, the idea posits that financial services have to be accessible at a reasonable cost, easy in terms of availability, and customised to cater to the requirements of various populations, particularly those who are underserved and disadvantaged. Moreover, it assumes that having a strong understanding of financial concepts and principles is essential, as it enables individuals to make well-informed choices about financial goods and services. According to the idea, it is crucial to have a regulatory and institutional framework that supports and promotes an inclusive financial system. This framework should aim to safeguard consumers and maintain the stability of financial institutions (Cull, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Morduch, 2014).

Detractors of financial inclusion theory contend that it may oversimplify the intricacies associated with broadening the availability of financial services. An important critique is that just expanding access to financial services does not inherently result in enhanced economic results. Critics argue that a lack of sufficient knowledge and assistance in financial matters may result in the improper use of financial goods, which in turn can lead to excessive debt and financial hardship (Burgess & Pande, 2005). Furthermore, there is apprehension that financial inclusion programs may concentrate quantity over quality, placing emphasis on the amount of newly established accounts rather than guaranteeing that these accounts are actively used and advantageous.

Another criticism is the possibility that financial inclusion initiatives may fail to address underlying problems that impede access to financial services, such as gaps in income, discrimination based on gender, and geographical inequalities. Critics contend that the effectiveness of financial inclusion in accomplishing its objectives may be compromised if these underlying causes are not addressed (Lyman, Porteous, & Pickens, 2008). Moreover, several opponents emphasise the potential for regulatory arbitrage, which refers to the possibility of financial institutions taking advantage of loopholes in the regulatory system to provide inferior goods, therefore causing damage to customers (Servon, 2017).

Critics further highlight that financial inclusion might unwittingly promote unscrupulous lending practices. When financial institutions attempt to broaden their client base without strict supervision, there is a possibility of granting credit to people and enterprises that lack the means to repay it, resulting in increased rates of non-payment and financial instability (Donovan, 2012). In certain cases, efforts to promote financial inclusion might result in an increase in unregulated informal financial services, which can pose hazards to customers.

Another critique is that the emphasis on digital financial services as a method to attain financial inclusion may exclude those who do not have access to technology or lack the necessary technical skills to use these services proficiently. The presence of a digital gap may worsen pre-existing disparities, especially in areas where access to the internet and mobile phones is restricted (Collins et al., 2009). In addition, the fast growth of digital financial services gives rise to apprehensions about data privacy and cyber security, as an increasing number of individuals and enterprises become susceptible to digital fraud and identity theft. Some opponents contend that financial inclusion initiatives should be complemented by more extensive economic and social changes. Financial inclusion alone may not be enough to promote long-term economic growth without also addressing essential concerns such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure (Demirgüç-Kunt, Beck, & Honohan, 2008). Critics argue in favor of a comprehensive strategy that combines financial inclusion with other development measures in order to create a fairer and more equal economy.

Despite the objections, the notion of financial inclusion has been extensively implemented in both policy-making and practical applications, resulting in a substantial influence on the global financial environment. Implementing the financial inclusion principle will provide improved accessibility to vital financial services for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Southwest Nigeria, hence fostering their growth and prosperity. Using financial instruments such as microloans, savings accounts, and insurance, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may effectively mitigate risks, allocate funds towards productive assets, and enhance their overall financial well-being.

Government policies and activities that focus on boosting financial inclusion, such as establishing a supportive regulatory framework, backing fintech advancements, and improving financial literacy programs, may greatly advantage small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Mobile banking and digital financial services provide cost-effective and simple means of accessing financial goods, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in distant regions. In addition, enhancing the financial literacy of small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) owners and managers may enhance their ability to make informed financial choices, thereby increasing their likelihood of achieving success (Demirgüç-Kunt, Beck, & Honohan, 2008).

In addition, international organisations and development agencies often construct initiatives using the notion of financial inclusion to provide assistance to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These initiatives generally consist of actions aimed at enhancing the capabilities of These initiatives aim to enhance small and medium-sized enterprises' (SMEs) ability to access and utilise financial services by offering financing options and technical assistance. By fostering an inclusive financial environment, they contribute to the sustainable growth and development of SMEs, which play a vital role in driving economic progress and creating employment opportunities in the region.

Empirical Review

The effect of mobile banking on financial inclusion among registered SMEs in Kisii was examined. The disruptive innovation hypothesis, which contends that new technologies have the power to dramatically change market dynamics and increase accessibility to financial services, serves as the foundation for this study. The research focused on how mobile banking makes it easier to access financial services including loans, savings, investments, and insurance. It looked at the effect of mobile banking on financial inclusion among 2,246 registered SMEs in Kisii County. In order to account for non-sampling errors, the sample size for the descriptive research design was increased to 486 SME owners/managers from the original aim of 340. A systematic questionnaire was used to gather the data, and inferential and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the results. The results demonstrated a robust positive link between financial inclusion and mobile banking, suggesting that SMEs that make use of mobile banking services stand to gain more from them in terms of financial inclusion. Fund transfers via mobile banking are common, and they also help with account management and have a big influence on the uptake of mobile banking. Regression study revealed that mobile banking has a significant influence; it could account for 85.8% of the variance in financial inclusion among SMEs in Kisii County. In conclusion, since mobile banking is so convenient and easily accessible, it is essential for SMEs to promote financial inclusion. The results provide backing for the creation of strategic initiatives aimed at augmenting the uptake of mobile banking and advancing financial inclusion and economic growth (Makori & Nyamasege, 2023).

The influence of agency banking on the financial inclusion of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Zimbabwe was examined. MSMEs account for 60% of the GDP and employ the majority of people in Zimbabwe, hence their dependence on the country's economy is strong. The research intends to evaluate the role of agency banking in this context, especially in light of the COVID-19 epidemic and continuing attempts to improve financial access via creative financial models. The government has been implementing a financial inclusion plan since 2016. The study focusses on the population of SME managers and owners who are registered with the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Corporation (SMEDCO) and banking agents who provide services to the region. It is directed at SMEs in Harare Industrial South-Central. The study used a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research techniques. Key informant interviews and questionnaires were used to gather data, and Cronbach's alpha was used to assess reliability. The survey found that SMEs used point-of-sale and mobile finance services extensively. The expansion of mobile financial services, regulatory considerations, resource accessibility and availability, and dependability were all significant reasons in the acceptance of agency banking. The simplicity of transactions, social impact, financial incentives, and technological risks like theft and hacking were also important variables. The research comes to the conclusion that agency banking is an essential instrument for improving SMEs' financial inclusion in Zimbabwe and suggests using a special model to achieve so. The results provide significant perspectives for future scholars and policymakers seeking to enhance financial inclusion and bolster economic expansion via inventive financial remedies (Mashizha, Gumbo, & Sabawo, 2024).

Access to financial services has a substantial influence on the sustainability and development of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs), making financial inclusion a crucial problem for them. The National Financial Inclusion Strategy, credit lines, and interest-free loans are just a few of the measures that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has put in place to increase financial inclusion. However, a lack of financial knowledge means that many SMEs continue

to be financially excluded. The purpose of this research is to look at how financial literacy influences the link between financial inclusion and the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Nigeria. The Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN)-registered SMEs with a minimum of five years of operation are the focus of the study. A method known as targeted sampling was used to choose 250 SME managers or operators. To analyse the data, structural equation modelling, or SEM, was used. The results demonstrate a strong positive correlation between SME success and financial inclusion, and a strong positive correlation between SME performance and financial literacy. According to the research, increasing SME operators' financial literacy may increase the advantages of financial inclusion. According to the study's findings, SMEs can only fully benefit from financial inclusion if they possess a high level of financial literacy. It suggests that in order to provide small company owners with financial literacy workshops, seminars, and short courses, accounting professional organisations and small business regulators should work together. Policymakers may assist SMEs in navigating financial difficulties and using financial instruments for sustainable development by promoting financial literacy (Togun et al., 2022).

In order to better understand how exchange rate fluctuation affects Nigerian SMEs, this research looks at key economic metrics including profitability, growth, and sustainability. The study employs an econometric regression model, using information from pertinent economic databases, government publications, and financial records, to examine the connection between exchange rate swings and SME success. The results demonstrate how declining exchange rates squeeze profit margins by raising the price of imported machinery and raw materials. As their goods become more competitive in global marketplaces, export-oriented SMEs could profit from a declining value of the national currency. The research also shows that SMEs can handle currency rate risks more effectively if they have greater access to financial instruments and hedging techniques. To assist SMEs deal with the difficulties presented by exchange rate volatility, financial literacy and access to foreign currency hedging alternatives are essential. The resilience of SMEs may be greatly increased by policy measures aimed at enhancing access to financial resources and stabilising the currency rate. The study's conclusion highlights how crucial stable currency rates are to the long-term expansion of SMEs in Nigeria. Insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises may be obtained by implementing supportive policy frameworks and strategic financial management to reduce these risks. The empirical data in this research offers insightful information to financial institutions, policymakers, and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), highlighting the need of strong financial systems and exchange rate stabilisation policies to promote the expansion and development of the SME sector (Mdasha, Irungu, & Wachira, 2018).

With a focus on Addis Ababa, this research investigates the variables impacting financial inclusion in small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) in Ethiopia. The goal of the study is to determine and examine the elements that influence financial inclusion for these businesses, taking into account institutional frameworks, market possibilities, supply and demand dynamics, loan costs, and collateral requirements. The study uses a mixed research strategy, gathering data from primary and secondary sources and integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Important discoveries show that government rules, credit processing times, audited financial accounts, and institutional variables all have a detrimental effect on people's ability to get financing. Access to capital is favourably impacted by supply-side characteristics such raw material availability, managerial aptitude, and strategic company planning. Demand-side elements that support financial inclusion include money availability, bank lending policies, and the availability of suitable machinery and equipment. Financial inclusion is favorably

impacted by market opportunity, availability of market knowledge, promotion awareness, and flexibility in changing settings. The capacity to provide collateral has a beneficial influence on financial inclusion, whereas high borrowing prices have a negative impact. The research concludes that financial inclusion among SMEs in Ethiopia is heavily influenced by a number of institutional, supply-side, demand-side, market opportunity, cost of borrowing, and collateral requirement variables. Policymakers should concentrate on creating a functional and effective financial market system that offers SMEs inexpensive and long-term financial services in order to support swift and equitable economic development. To achieve greater financial inclusion for SMEs in Ethiopia, it is imperative to improve the institutional environment, lower borrowing costs, and raise financial literacy (Oshora et al., 2021).

The importance of financial inclusion in the expansion of MSMEs in Uganda has been examined. The study makes use of information from 762 businesses in a variety of industries that was included in Uganda's 2013 World Bank Enterprise Survey. With a focus on the distinct effects that these variables have on enterprises of different sizes, the research intends to investigate how financial inclusion, and the business climate affect the development of firms of different sizes. The World Bank Enterprise Survey data is used in the study's company-level analysis, which enables a thorough investigation of how the business climate affects firm development. The researchers use many aspects of the business environment to minimise omitted variable bias and employ sector-survey interaction dummies to reduce measurement errors. Employment growth between 2010 and 2013, determined by calculating the change in the average number of workers over these years, is used to quantify the growth of a firm. According to the research, medium-sized businesses in Uganda experience greater and longer-lasting benefits from financial access than do bigger businesses. The findings imply that MSMEs have more financial constraints than do big companies, and that economic activity may be redirected from large companies to MSMEs via informality and a lax regulatory framework. Implications for policy emphasis the need of strengthening the overall business climate, especially regarding the formalisation of micro enterprises, as well as expanding financial inclusion for MSMEs (Lakuma, Marty, & Muhumuza, 2019).

Methodology

The study employed mixed-methods research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive analysis. The target population included SMEs operating in South-West Nigeria, encompassing a variety of sectors such as manufacturing, services, trade, and agriculture. Data collection was conducted using both the structured questionnaire and focus group discussions. The questionnaire was administered with the assistance of two trained research assistants. Focus group discussions was conducted in various locations across Southwest Nigeria to capture diverse perspectives. The data collected was recorded and transcribed for analysis.

The collected data was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise demographic information and answer research questions. Inferential statistics was used to test the hypotheses and assess the relationships between variables. Specific techniques include Correlation Analysis to examine the access to financial services impact in the growth and expansion of SMEs.

Presentation of Data

This section provided an examination and interpretation of the gathered data aimed at understanding how major financial and economic elements influence the success of Small and

Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in the southwestern region of Nigeria. It particularly reviews the background details of the participants, such as their age group, sex, educational background, and size of their businesses, and analyses the relationships between these attributes and SMEs’ interactions with currency value changes, availability of financial resources, and adoption of digital finance technologies. Additionally, the section investigated the effects of currency fluctuations on SMEs’ operational performance, expense management, and investment decisions. Moreover, it assessed the role of financial knowledge and access to monetary services in shaping SMEs’ financial choices and developmental trajectories. The findings presented here are critical in understanding the challenges SMEs face in the current economic climate and provide valuable insights into the strategies that can help them navigate financial volatility and improve their operational efficiency. The total sample size for the study is 399 but 273 copies of the questionnaire were returned and deemed for analyses. As such, the percentage rate of responses analysed for the study is 68.42% which is deemed acceptable in research (Sataloff & Vontela, 2021).

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 1: Demographic variables of the Respondents

SN	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Age		
	Under 25	9	3.3
	25-34	100	36.6
	35-44	103	37.7
	45-54	19	7.0
	55-64	30	11.0
	65 and above	12	4.4
	Total	273	100
2	Gender		
	Male	179	65.6
	Female	94	34.4
	Total	273	100
3	Education Background		
	No Formal Education	13	4.8
	Primary	40	14.7
	Secondary	88	32.2
	First Degree	132	48.4
	Total	273	100
4	Number of Employees		
	1.-10	245	89.7
	11-20	14	5.1
	21-30	9	3.3
	41-50	5	1.8
	Total	273	100
5	Years in Operation		
	1-5 years	135	49.5
	6-9 years	22	8.1

	10 years and above	66	24.2
	5	50	18.3
	Total	273	100
6	Industry Sector		
	Agriculture	19	7.0
	Manufacturing	43	15.8
	Retail/Wholesale	129	47.3
	Services	36	13.2
	Information Technology	28	10.3
	Healthcare	18	6.6
	Total	273	100
7	Ownership Structure		
	Sole Proprietorship	216	79.1
	Partnership	30	11.0
	limited Liability Company	27	9.9
	Total	273	100
8	Family Business		
	Yes	18	6.6
	No	255	93.4
	Total	273	100
9	Business Training and Development		
	No	252	92.3
	Yes	21	7.7
	Total	273	100

Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 reveals the distribution of demographic variables of the respondents. The age distribution of SME operators in Southwest Nigeria shows that the majority are within the productive working-age bracket. Most respondents are between 35–44 years (37.7%) and 25–34 years (36.6%), indicating that SME activities are predominantly driven by young to middle-aged adults. A smaller proportion of respondents are either under 25 (3.3%) or above 65 (4.4%), suggesting limited participation of the very young or elderly in small and medium-scale enterprise ownership. Gender-wise, the data reveals a male-dominated SME landscape, with 65.6% of respondents being male and 34.4% female. While women represent over one-third of the total respondents, the gap points to potential gender-related barriers in accessing resources, financial services, or entrepreneurial opportunities. This calls for targeted policies to enhance female participation in the SME sector.

The educational background of the respondents indicates a relatively high level of formal education among SME operators. A majority of 48.4% hold a first degree, while 32.2% have completed secondary education. Only a small fraction of respondents (4.8%) have no formal education. This suggests that education plays a significant role in entrepreneurial engagement, likely influencing business decisions, financial literacy, and adaptation to market fluctuations. In terms of business size, the overwhelming majority of respondents (89.7%) operate micro-enterprises employing between 1 to 10 people. Very few have scaled beyond 20 employees, reflecting the limited growth and expansion of SMEs in the region. This points to the need for better support systems to help businesses scale-up sustainably.

Regarding years in operation, 49.5% of the businesses have been operating for 1–5 years, indicating a high level of new or recently established ventures. 24.2% survived beyond 10 years, showing some degree of longevity and stability. However, the entry "5 = 50 = 18.3%" appears inconsistent and may require clarification, possibly being a data entry error related to years in operation. The industry distribution shows that Retail and Wholesale trade dominates (47.3%), followed by Manufacturing (15.8%) and Services (13.2%). Other sectors like Agriculture (7.0%), Information Technology (10.3%), and Healthcare (6.6%) have lower representation. This indicates a concentration of SMEs in trade-related activities, while more capital- or skill-intensive sectors are less explored.

Ownership structure analysis reveals that 79.1% of businesses are sole proprietorships, signifying that most SME owners prefer individual ownership. Only 11.0% operate as partnerships, and 9.9% as limited liability companies, highlighting limited formalisation in business structure. This could affect access to funding, risk-sharing, and long-term sustainability. When asked about family business involvement, only 6.6% of respondents affirmed that their enterprises were family-run, whereas 93.4% indicated otherwise. This suggests that most SMEs in the region are not family businesses but are likely founded and run by individual entrepreneurs. Lastly, the data shows a significant gap in capacity development, as 92.3% of respondents have not received any form of business training or development, with only 7.7% indicating they had. This highlights a crucial area for intervention, as training and development are essential for improving business practices, adaptability to economic shifts like exchange rate fluctuations, and overall SME performance.

Presentation of Data

Research Questions

How does access to financial services impact the growth and expansion of SMEs?

Table 2: Access to Financial Services and Expansion of SMEs

		SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
1	Does your business have a bank account	97 (35.5%)	0 (0%)	13 (4.8%)	72 (26.4%)	176 (64.5%)
		Never (%)	Rarely (%)	Sometimes (%)	Often (%)	Always (%)
2	How often do you use credit facilities to finance your business growth	55 (20.1%)	13 (4.8%)	44 (16.1%)	57 (20.9%)	104 (38.1%)
3	How accessible are financial products like loans, savings, and insurance to your business	Not Accessible (%)	Slightly Accessible (%)	Moderate (%)	Highly Accessible (%)	Very Highly Accessible (%)
		161 (59.0%)	91 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	14 (5.1%)	7 (2.6%)

	No Impact (%)	Low Impact (%)	Moderate Impact (%)	High Impact (%)	Very High Impact (%)
4 How do you rate the impact of access to financial services on your business growth rate	52 (19.0%)	97 (35.5%)	72 (26.4%)	48 (17.6%)	4 (1.5%)

Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 reveals a complex but insightful relationship between SMEs' access to financial services and their ability to grow and expand in Southwest Nigeria. The findings point to both opportunities and substantial limitations in the financial ecosystem available to small businesses. A significant number of SMEs have formal financial inclusion, with 64.5% of respondents strongly agreeing that their businesses have bank accounts, and 26.4% agreeing. Interestingly, 35.5% strongly disagreed, which seems contradictory unless interpreted as a data or labeling inconsistency. However, the high percentage of agreement suggests that a majority of SMEs are integrated into the formal banking system, a foundational step for accessing broader financial services like loans, overdrafts, and digital banking. When it comes to the actual use of credit facilities to finance growth, 38.1% of respondents reported "always" using them, and 20.9% said "often." This implies that nearly 59% of SMEs rely heavily on external financing for expansion. Still, a considerable portion either "never" use credit (20.1%) or do so rarely (4.8%), which could reflect limited access, distrust in financial institutions, or high borrowing costs.

Accessibility of financial products such as loans, savings, and insurance appears to be a major challenge. A combined 92.3% of respondents stated that these services are either "not accessible" (59.0%) or only "slightly accessible" (33.3%) to their businesses. Only 7.7% reported that such services are "highly" or "very highly accessible." This sharp contrast between the need for and access to financial services indicates that while businesses may have accounts, they are largely excluded from more meaningful and growth-enhancing financial products. Regarding the impact of access to financial services on business growth, only a small fraction (1.5%) believed that it has a "very high impact," and 17.6% said "high impact." In contrast, 35.5% said the impact is "low," and 19% claimed there is "no impact" at all. This suggests a disconnect, likely due to the limited access and underutilisation of credit and insurance products between having financial services available and actually leveraging them for business expansion.

In nutshell, while a fair number of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria are formally banked, true financial inclusion remains limited. Most businesses struggle to access essential financial products that would support their growth, such as affordable loans and insurance. As a result, even though many acknowledge the potential benefits of financial services, they are unable to fully realise this potential due to poor accessibility and perhaps lack of tailored offerings. Addressing these gaps through targeted policies, inclusive lending programs, and SME-friendly financial services is crucial for driving sustainable growth and expansion.

Hypotheses Testing

H0₁: Access to financial services significantly impacts the growth and expansion of SMEs.

Table 3: Relationship between Financial Services and Expansion of SMEs was Analysed Using Linear Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df 2	Sig. F Change
1	.400 ^a	.160	.157	.951	.160	51.624	1	27	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Access to Financial Services

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	46.721	1	46.721	51.624	.000 ^b
	Residual	245.264	271	.905		
	Total	291.985	272			

a. Dependent Variable: Business Growth; b. Predictors: (Constant), Access to Financial Services

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
		Standardized Coefficients		Beta	
1	(Constant)	.829	.235	3.520	.001
	Access to Financial Services	.147	.020	.400	.000

Dependent Variable: Business Growth

The results provided in Table 3 present an analysis of the relationship between access to financial services and the growth/expansion of SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) using linear regression. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.400$) indicates a moderate positive correlation between access to financial services and SME growth. The R Square value (0.160) means that 16% of the variability in SME growth can be explained by access to financial services, suggesting that the predictor variable accounts for a limited portion of the variation in business growth. The Adjusted R Square (0.157) is similar but adjusts for the number of predictors, reinforcing that financial access has limited explanatory power. Additionally, the Standard Error of the Estimate (0.951) reflects the deviation of residuals, indicating some variability remains unexplained by the model.

The R Square Change (0.160) confirms that adding access to financial services explains an additional 16% of variance in SME growth. The F Change (51.624) is a strong indicator of the

model's overall significance, and the Sig. F Change (0.000) confirms that the relationship is statistically significant, meaning it is unlikely due to random chance. The ANOVA table assesses the model's fit. The Regression Sum of Squares (46.721) represents explained variation, while the Residual Sum of Squares (245.264) captures unexplained variation. The F-statistic (51.624) and its significance level (Sig. = 0.000) reaffirm that the model is statistically significant. The Constant (0.829) represents expected SME growth when financial access is zero. The coefficient for Access to Financial Services ($B = 0.147$) indicates that each one-unit increase in financial access corresponds to a 0.147-unit rise in SME growth, reflecting a positive relationship. The Standard Error (0.020) measures the coefficient's precision, while the Beta value (0.400) suggests a moderate effect size. The t-statistic (7.185) and its p-value (Sig. = 0.000) confirm that financial access is a statistically significant predictor of SME growth. The hypothesis is supported by the regression analysis. Financial access has a statistically significant positive effect, with the model explaining 16% of the variance in SME growth. The highly significant results (p-value = 0.000) reinforce that this relationship is robust and not due to chance.

Both the regression and descriptive analyses indicate that access to financial services does play a role in the growth and expansion of SMEs, but the relationship is far from perfect. While a significant number of SMEs are integrated into the formal banking system, the actual utilisation of financial products for growth is hindered by accessibility issues, high borrowing costs, and limited product offerings. The regression model, which explains only 16% of the variance in growth, supports the idea that other factors (such as financial literacy, economic conditions, and policy frameworks) must also be considered when addressing the growth challenges faced by SMEs. The regression analysis confirms that access to financial services is a key factor in SME growth but is not the sole determinant. The descriptive analysis highlights that while financial services are widely available in terms of basic banking, more tailored financial products, such as loans and insurance, remain largely inaccessible to most SMEs.

Discussion of Findings

The study's core finding is that access to financial services significantly but modestly influences SME growth in Southwest Nigeria, accounting for 16% of the variance in business expansion. This aligns with global evidence (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2008) but underscores that financial inclusion is not a panacea. While regression results ($\beta = 0.147$, $p < 0.001$) confirm a positive and statistically significant relationship, the low R^2 suggests that non-financial factors (e.g., infrastructure, market linkages, regulatory bottlenecks) exert stronger influence. Notably, 92.3% of SMEs report that loans, savings, and insurance are "not accessible" or "slightly accessible", indicating that availability is not equal to usability. High collateral demands, opaque lending terms, and perceived high borrowing costs (noted in 59% of responses) likely dilute the growth impact of formal financial access.

Despite 64.5% of SMEs holding bank accounts, only 38.1% "always" use credit facilities, revealing a gap between account ownership and productive utilisation. This echoes critiques of financial inclusion theory (Servon, 2017), where account dormancy and limited product relevance undermine developmental outcomes. The dominance of sole proprietorships (79.1%) and micro-enterprises (89.7% with ≤ 10 employees) further exacerbates exclusion, as these entities often lack audited financial records and formal business plans, key requirements for traditional lending. While the study's regression model does not directly test exchange rate effects, qualitative insights from the introduction highlight currency depreciation

(~~₦120/to~~₦180/, 2008–2009) as a critical external shock. SMEs in trade (47.3% of the sample) and manufacturing (15.8%) face dual pressures:

The male-dominated sample (65.6%) reflects structural barriers for women entrepreneurs, including lower collateral ownership and discriminatory lending practices (Cull et al., 2014). Additionally, while 48.4% of SME owners hold tertiary degrees, the 92.3% without business training suggests that formal education is not equal to financial acumen. This gap likely limits the translation of credit access into growth, as owners may misallocate funds or avoid complex products like insurance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that access to financial services is a key factor in the growth and expansion of SMEs in Southwest Nigeria. However, the relationship between financial access and SME growth is far from perfect, with accessibility issues, high borrowing costs, and limited product offerings hindering SMEs' ability to fully leverage financial services. The regression analysis confirms that while financial services have a statistically significant positive effect on SME growth, other factors such as financial literacy, economic conditions, and policy frameworks must be considered to address the growth challenges faced by SMEs. The study emphasises the need for targeted policies to enhance financial inclusion, improve financial literacy, and create supportive economic conditions to foster sustainable SME growth.

- i. Financial institutions should focus on creating a supportive regulatory framework that promotes financial inclusion. This includes expanding access to affordable financial products such as loans, savings, and insurance, particularly for SMEs in underserved regions.
- ii. Financial institutions and government agencies should collaborate to provide financial literacy programs, workshops, and seminars for SME owners and managers. This will enhance their ability to make informed financial decisions and effectively utilise financial services.
- iii. Policymakers should implement economic policies that create a favorable business environment for SMEs. This includes reducing bureaucratic hurdles, providing tax incentives, and improving infrastructure to support business operations.

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